

ENCOURAGING CHILDREN TO READ BOOKS

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ABSTRACT

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This article talks about how to make children interested in books, bring the culture of reading to the world of children, how many measures implemented in our country in this regard are invisible to the general public, and about the achievements.

The book is an integral part of the culture of humanity and society, and has been a means of educating people and their intellectual development in all periods of human development.

In the development of human thinking, books and writing have always been companions. Although some forms of culture and enlightenment were based on oral communication, it was only after the emergence of writing that it reached the present day and became a reality.

The book is the most reliable and the most convenient means of communication created by mankind. Perfect human upbringing, people's spirituality, culture, manners, level of knowledge, occupying a special place in society depends only on the knowledge obtained from books, because it is the most perfect tool for preserving and spreading human intelligence and knowledge. . The book allows people to learn about the achievements of mankind, restores relations, harmony, and mutual kindness between peoples. It serves to establish and strengthen peace in the world. "The book is the soul and heart of any knowledge, the beginning of any science," said the German writer S. Schweig. Books have been and will remain the most necessary thing for all times, the balm of souls, the treasure of knowledge, the fountain of wisdom.

The core of the words "book", "reading", "library" is actually derived from Arabic and serves one purpose, that is, to enrich human spirituality. The reforms implemented in our country to increase the reading culture of young people are not in vain, therefore, the maturity of the future generation is determined by acquiring knowledge and being educated. In this regard, on January 12, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, announced a decree "Directed to increase book reading and reading culture". This, in turn, is an important factor contributing to the increase in the level of reading in our country and the publication of new books with content. Using such opportunities wisely, reading rich works from new editions allows young people to develop their consciousness, deepen their thinking, and have their own independent opinion.

It is also important that the society and environment to which the child belongs is inclined to read books. A person who has never held a book in his hand has no right or reason to advise or order a child to "read a book"! "Children are educated not by our words, but by our actions," Makarenko said the same truth. Children who love reading grow up in homes where books are read. Of course, this is not the absolute truth.

In most families, the situation is roughly as follows: on Mother's Day, she is busy with household chores, and rushes to make out with the neighboring women until she finds a little free time. The time allotted for watching television, serials, attending weddings, etc. is not enough for reading books. And the father works all day, comes to eat in the evening, pretends to watch TV, and then goes to sleep. Discussing the books read, giving advice on what books to read, unfortunately, is very rare in families. In public: not to mention the reading of books in boulevards, vehicles, waiting rooms, stations, hospitals. I wish you could reach out to such places and put books where you can, and read them in your free time.

These words are not the product of my personal imagination at all. In many countries, similar social projects have been launched, where people put the books they have read on special shelves that are open to everyone and free of charge. He can take whatever work he wants from there. As our late writer Asqad Mukhtar said, books are wealth, not what is bought, but what is read. Looking at it from this point of view, this priceless wealth can be shared with everyone.

It should also be noted that the 5 initiatives put forward by the President have become an important factor that further supports the youth today. "Organizing systematic work on raising the morale of young people, widely promoting reading among them" is becoming an important program. Acquaintance with the book, reading it, gives a person special pleasure.

While reading, the reader gets to know the book more closely, begins to form an idea about its scientific and artistic value, thinks, and develops reading culture. To improve the reading culture of our country due to the special attention paid to it, "Young Reader", "Festival of Book Readers" held in secondary schools, universities, all educational institutions, viewing contests, modern bookstores opening in recreation areas and libraries opening in remote villages plays an important role in satisfying the spiritual and intellectual needs of the young generation, in getting familiar with books.

In children's reading pedagogy, the growth of reading according to age is divided into the following stages: childhood 6-9 years; adolescence 12-13 years old; the transition from adolescence to adulthood is considered to be 14 years. The age limit of this category is flexible, that is, according to the formation of the socio-psychological conditions of the reader, a 10-year-old child can be added to the category of a teenage reader, and a 14-year-old reader is a reader transitioning to adolescence, depending on the specific typological characteristics. can be added to the category

The main goal of raising the reading culture is to educate a cultured person. Art and literature are of great importance in educating a cultured person. Each of us must contribute to this. After all, today's children are our future.

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